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Supervised Machine Learning Approach for Prediction of Occult Lymph Node Metastasis in T1-T2 Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma

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This study aimed to assess and compare four machine learning (ML) based classifiers in predicting occult cervical lymph node metastasis (LNM) in clinically node-negative (cNO), T1-T2 papillary thyroid carcinoma (PTC) patients.

The study cohort included 288 PTC patients who underwent total thyroidectomy and prophylactic central neck dissection with sentinel lymph node biopsy performed for lateral LNM identification. The classifiers, namely k-Nearest Neighbor (k-NN), Support Vector Machines, Decision Tree, and Logistic Regression were developed using patients' demographic and clinicopathological variables. Evaluation metrics such as area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC), sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values (PPV and NPV), accuracy, and F1 and F2 scores were utilized for model comparison.

The final ML classifier was selected based on achieving the highest specificity and the lowest degree of overfitting while maintaining a sensitivity of 95%. Among the evaluated models, the k-NN emerged as the best-performing, demonstrating an AUC of 0.72. The sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, F1, and F2 scores were 98%, 27%, 56%, 93%, 72%, and 85%, respectively. Furthermore, a web application was developed allowing users to predict the potential of cervical LNM and explore possibilities for further model development.

The k-NN classifier incorporating patients' clinicopathological information shows potential in predicting LNM. Improved prediction models are necessary to identify patients at higher risk of LNM, guiding appropriate postsurgical treatment for high-risk individuals while minimizing unnecessary interventions for low-risk patients.

Keywords: machine learning, papillary thyroid carcinoma, lymph node metastasis

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